

MAPPING OF SEAFLOOR MARINE MACROLITTER DISTRIBUTION IN THE VENICE COASTAL AREA

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Marine litter is a significant and growing pollutant in the oceans. In recent years, the number of studies and initiatives trying to assess and tackle the global threat of marine litter has grown exponentially. It is estimated that about 70% of marine debris sinks to the seabed with unknown consequences. For this reason, developing new techniques and protocols for mapping and monitoring the presence of marine litter on the seafloor is of fundamental importance. Within the EU co-founded H2020 Smart technology for Marine Litter Sustainable Removal and Management (MAELSTROM) project, the presence of marine litter on the seafloor was investigated in two highly impacted sites in the Venice coastal area: a) an abandoned mussel farm at sea, b) a channel close to the historical city center in the Venice Lagoon. The marine litter was mapped and classified through high resolution multibeam echosounder mapping and videos. The marine litter items were visually identified both on the seafloor and the water column. Moreover, a dedicated workflow in ArcGIS was developed to extract the litter items starting from the high-resolution Digital Terrain Model (DTM) (5-10 cm horizontal resolution) extracted from the bathymetry data. At the same time, drop frames and pictures from the seafloor as ground truth were collected. Based on the obtained maps, we found in the mussel farm site at sea a high density of waste deriving from aquaculture activities both on the bottom and in the water column, such as ropes, buoys, nets and mooring blocks. In the lagoon site, instead, we found an accumulation of urban debris on the seafloor, such as tyres, piles, small sunken boats, crates, etc. The acquired data were used for the design of a specific Seabed Cleaning platform based on a cable robot technology aimed at removing the identified marine litter, which will be tested in the next months at both sites. The efficacy of the removal operations and their environmental impact on the benthic habitat communities will be also assessed through periodic monitoring campaigns over the next two years.